

MEDICAL AND SOCIAL REHABILITATION OF PATIENTS WITH POLYDRUG ADDICTION: EXPERIENCE IN TREATING OPIOID-HASHISH DEPENDENCE

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Abstract. *This article examines the medical and social rehabilitation of patients with polydrug addiction resulting from opioid-hashish dependence. Modern treatment approaches are analyzed, including pharmacotherapy, psychotherapeutic interventions, and social adaptation programs. Special attention is given to comprehensive rehabilitation methods aimed at reducing the risk of relapse and restoring patients' social functioning. Based on treatment experience, key factors influencing the success of rehabilitation are identified, along with prospects for improving rehabilitation programs by considering the medical, psychological, and social aspects of addiction.*

Keywords: *polydrug addiction, opiates, hashish, addiction syndrome, treatment, psychotherapy, rehabilitation.*

In recent years, there has been a clear trend toward polydependence on various psychoactive substances [6, 12, 16]. Epidemiological studies indicate that the spread of drug addiction occurs primarily among adolescents and young adults [8, 11, 18, 19]. The most socially prosperous segments of the population are becoming involved in drug use, and the number of female drug users is increasing [1, 7, 13]. There is a growing use of highly addictive substances such as heroin, cocaine, and stimulants [3].

The clinical picture of drug addiction is changing due to the spread of synthetic drugs produced in illegal laboratories, drug substitutes, and the combined use of two or more psychoactive substances [4, 10, 17]. For instance, cases of psychosis have been reported among opioid users, which were previously absent in "classical" opioid monodrug addiction [9, 20]. The mortality rate associated with psychoactive substances is also rising.

The combined use of multiple narcotic substances not only worsens the course of addiction but also significantly reduces the effectiveness of treatment [14, 15]. Opioid-hashish polydrug addiction, which is widespread in Uzbekistan and other Central Asian countries, has attracted researchers' attention, as the diagnostic criteria for this form of the disease remain insufficiently developed, and issues related to its clinical presentation, progression, treatment, and medical-social rehabilitation are poorly covered [2, 5].

Purpose of the study. Assessment of the effectiveness of therapeutic and rehabilitation measures provided to patients with addiction syndrome caused by the combined use of opioids and hashish.

Material and research methods. 100 patients with opioid-hashish polydrug addiction (90 men and 10 women) were examined. The sole criterion for patient selection was the combined abuse of opioid (heroin) and cannabinoid (hashish) substances, along with the presence of dependence syndrome on both drugs (ICD-10 code F19).

The examination of patients was conducted using clinical-psychopathological, clinical-follow-up, and experimental-psychological methods. Clinical observation included a thorough assessment of mental, somatic, and neurological conditions at different stages of the disease (withdrawal syndrome, post-withdrawal state, remission, and relapse). Follow-up data was obtained for 40 patients within a period ranging from 3 months to 2 years after discharge from the hospital.

Results and Discussion. The age of the patients at the time of the examination ranged from 18 to 63 years. The average age of the patients was 32.3 ± 6.8 years. The duration of drug use (including occasional use) at the time of the examination varied from 1 to 41 years, with an average of 16.1 ± 8.6 years.

The duration of opioid drug abuse ranged from 2 months to 30 years, with an average duration of 8.0 ± 6.8 years. The stage of hashish addiction before the introduction to opioids was classified according to the criteria described in the literature.

An individual therapeutic and rehabilitation plan was developed for each patient, which included a comprehensive set of biological and socio-psychological interventions, with a clearly defined sequence of therapeutic technologies. The treatment and rehabilitation program consists of the following components: 1) level of impact (biological, psychological, social); 2) main targets of intervention; 3) type of therapy; 4) methods and means of intervention.

At the biological level, the main targets of intervention were withdrawal syndrome, pathological cravings for opioids, hashish, psychopathic, and intellectual-memory disorders that developed because of drug use, somatic complications of polydrug addiction, and comorbid diseases in the acute phase. The leading type of therapy was pathogenetically oriented pharmacological intervention, with an emphasis on the use of drugs capable of affecting the neurochemical mechanisms of addiction.

Since after discontinuing drug use, the predominant symptoms in opioid-hashish polydrug addiction were those of opioid withdrawal syndrome, treatment began with alleviating withdrawal symptoms. The following medications were used: alpha-2 adrenergic agonists for the central nervous system (clonidine); neuroleptics with strong antipsychotic effects (haloperidol, aminazine, or tizerzin); benzodiazepines (diazepam); anticonvulsants (carbamazepine); sodium oxybutyrate; mildronate; magnesium sulfate; non-narcotic analgesics; vitamin therapy; symptomatic treatment.

After the acute manifestations of opioid withdrawal syndrome were managed, patients continued to receive vitamin therapy, symptomatic treatment aimed at restoring impaired internal organ functions, and physiotherapy procedures. The treatment plan also included nootropics (piracetam) to reduce asthenia and improve cognitive functions.

However, the main target in the post-withdrawal period became the pathological craving for drugs and the associated intensification of psychopathic-like disorders. As a result, the spectrum of psychotropic medications used significantly expanded. The choice of psychotropic drugs was made based on individual indications, depending on the dominant components of pathological drug cravings.

In cases of intense pathological craving, for opioids (predominant over cravings for hashish in the post-withdrawal period) with pronounced dysphoria and psychopathic-like behavior, strong neuroleptics were preferred (haloperidol or trifluoperazine combined with aminazine or tizerzin,

azaleptol, risperidone). These neuroleptics were combined with anticonvulsants (carbamazepine) and potent tranquilizers (diazepam, phenazepam).

In cases where depressive disorders predominated in the craving structure, tricyclic antidepressants with sedative effects (amitriptyline) or selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (fluvoxamine) were added to the treatment regimen, combined with neuroleptics that had minimal side effects on the extrapyramidal system (azaleptol, risperidone).

In some cases, to suppress pathological cravings, improve sleep function, and reduce asthenic disorders, manipulative psychotherapy strategies (hypnosuggestive therapy) were used alongside pharmacological treatment. Improvement in the patient's mental and somatic condition, as well as the suppression of pathological drug cravings, were necessary conditions for transitioning to the next, psychological level of intervention, where the primary targets became the patient's critical stance toward drug abuse, motivation for treatment, cessation of drug use, personal status, self-esteem, and competence in interpersonal relationships. At this stage, these tasks could no longer be addressed with pharmacological methods, so the focus shifted toward psychotherapeutic interventions.

Psychotherapeutic intervention was a combination of manipulative techniques aimed at changing the patient's behavior and person-centered methods focused on personality correction and further development. Depending on the nature of the psychotherapeutic impact, the relationship between the therapist and the patient was based on the "guidance–partnership" principle (when using manipulative techniques) or "partnership" (when applying person-centered methods).

Among the manipulative methods, hypnotherapy continued to be used, which not only suppressed pathological cravings for drugs but also, to a certain extent, addressed issues of attitude formation, self-esteem enhancement, and the dismantling of undesirable behavior patterns. Behavioral psychotherapy was also applied in the form of various types of socio-psychological training (training in communication skills, sensitivity, stress resistance, and assertive behavior). An effective therapeutic environment, based on behavioral psychotherapy principles, was created in the rehabilitation unit.

To combat the exacerbation of pathological cravings for drugs, patients were taught methods of self-regulation and tension release (autogenic training, Jacobson's progressive muscle relaxation). Given the predominance of unproductive coping strategies on an emotional level, frequent avoidance of constructive problem solving, the tendency to shift responsibility for their difficulties onto others, and an increased level of aggressiveness, training in self-regulation techniques and stress-coping skills was considered especially important for the subsequent prevention of relapse.

Among the personality development methods used were group psychotherapy in small groups, individual and group rational psychotherapy, art therapy, gestalt therapy, and transactional analysis techniques.

The development of criticism toward drug addiction (especially cannabis dependence) and the formation of a commitment to complete abstinence from psychoactive substances were carried out using rational psychotherapy and motivational interviewing. In our opinion, motivational interviewing should be considered the more appropriate approach. The use of direct persuasion, which underlies individual rational psychotherapy, in most cases encountered unconscious resistance from the patient, who tended to deny the harm of cannabis use in order to satisfy their

pathological need for euphoria after ceasing opioid intake. Motivational interviewing, on the other hand, made it possible to overcome resistance and encourage the patient to reflect on changing their behavior regarding cannabis consumption.

Rational psychotherapy was conducted in a group format (group discussions), incorporating patients who recognized the harm of cannabinoid dependence. Through discussions, these patients provided valuable information about the harmful consequences of using not only opioids but also hashish, thereby positively influencing the attitudes of other patients toward the use of this drug.

At the social level, the primary targets of intervention were the patients' family and occupational adaptation, with the therapeutic approach combining psychotherapy and socially oriented interventions. The main methods and tools for achieving the desired outcome included family psychotherapy (including work with co-dependent family members), occupational therapy, computer skills training and cultural and wellness activities.

Progressing to each new level did not mean a complete cessation of the activities from the previous level. On the contrary, earlier interventions were integrated into the set of measures at each subsequent stage. Thus, emphasizing psychotherapy methods did not exclude the continuation of pharmacological treatment aimed at suppressing pathological cravings and correcting psychopathic-like and intellectual-mnestic disorders.

Pharmacological treatment for patients with opioid-hashish polydrug addiction must be prolonged due to the persistence of personality changes. The study showed that to enhance the effectiveness of therapeutic and rehabilitation measures, strict adherence to a specific sequence of interventions is necessary. As long as the intensity of pathological drug cravings remains high, it is impossible to develop critical awareness and change attitudes. Until the patient makes a decision to change their behavior, it is difficult to orient them toward a healthy lifestyle or begin personality correction. Without personality correction, social readaptation and reintegration into society become unattainable.

To achieve stable remission, it is essential to consolidate the results of medical and social rehabilitation and to conduct long-term relapse prevention measures in outpatient settings.

Given the low rehabilitation potential of patients with opioid-hashish polydrug addiction, we believe that the treatment and rehabilitation process should begin in specialized addiction treatment hospitals and continue for an extended period (at least three months). Shorter treatment durations do not lead to the necessary changes in personality status. Subsequently, inpatient care can transition to a partial hospitalization or outpatient setting.

Thus, within the framework of a three-month inpatient rehabilitation program, patients with opioid-hashish polydrug addiction underwent the following stages:

1) Therapeutic and diagnostic stage, combining diagnosis and interventions at the biological level. This stage was conducted in a narcology department and lasted for at least two weeks.

2) Core rehabilitation stage, including interventions at both the biological and psychological levels. The duration of this stage was no less than 1.5 months.

3) Final stage, integrating interventions at the biological, psychological, and social levels, with an emphasis on socio-therapeutic measures. This stage lasted for at least one month.

In the post-rehabilitation period, outpatient measures were implemented to prevent relapses and breakdowns in opioid-hashish polydrug addiction.

Of the total number of patients studied, 66 individuals with opioid-hashish polydrug addiction completed only the first stage of the program. A total of 34 patients were motivated to undergo the core rehabilitation process, and 17 patients successfully completed all three stages of the program. The program's outcomes were evaluated based on clinical data and follow-up (catamnestic) research.

Follow-up data were obtained for 40 patients, of whom 26 had completed only the first stage (medication treatment), while 14 had completed the second and third stages of the program. The study revealed that 42.3% of patients who received only pharmacological therapy resumed cannabis use immediately after discharge, quickly followed by the reintroduction of opioid drugs. For 46.2% of these patients, the duration of remission, (complete abstinence from opioids and cannabis) did not exceed 1–3 months, and only 11.5% remained drug-free for 4–6 months.

In contrast, none of the patients who completed the second and third stages of the rehabilitation program relapsed immediately after treatment ($p < 0.001$). All of these patients experienced remission periods of varying lengths: up to 3 months in 64.3% of cases ($p > 0.05$), more than 3 to 6 months in 14.3% ($p > 0.05$), more than 6 to 12 months in 7.1% ($p > 0.05$), more than 1 year in 14.3% ($p > 0.05$).

These findings suggest that a comprehensive, multi-stage rehabilitation approach significantly improves treatment outcomes, leading to longer remission periods and reducing the likelihood of immediate relapse.

Conclusions. The treatment of patients with opioid-hashish polydrug addiction should be based on a multilevel approach to therapeutic interventions, addressing biological, psychological, and social aspects of personality functioning. This requires a diverse and individualized rehabilitation process, incorporating various psychotherapeutic methods and techniques, as well as comprehensive social readaptation and reintegration measures. Successful rehabilitation is only possible under the condition of complete abstinence from drug use.

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